

FATIGUE RESPONSE OF THE UNIDIRECTIONAL AND CROSS-PLY SCS-6/TI-15-3 MMC

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Abstract

This paper investigates the fatigue response of the unidirectional and cross-ply SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC laminates under fully-reversed ($R = -1$) loading conditions. Two control modes were studied: load and strain. For the 0° laminate, a comparison was made between the fatigue behavior of a 32 ply and an 8 ply laminate. The 8 ply laminate, using an anti-buckling guide, exhibited the same fatigue behavior as the thicker material. Also, the fatigue life was independent of loading mode for both the 0° and $0/90$ lay-ups. Finally, a single fatigue curve was developed for the unidirectional and cross-ply laminates based on the maximum stress in the 0° plies.

Introduction

Many components in future aerospace applications will require the use of advanced materials capable of withstanding severe thermomechanical environments. One class of materials that has been identified for use in these environments is titanium based metal matrix composites (MMCs). The type of loading imposed on these materials will be either load-controlled, strain-controlled, or a combination of both. Thus it is desirable to understand the similarities and differences in the behavior of a MMC when subjected to fatigue under these conditions.

An extensive amount of work has been conducted on MMCs over the last decade. In the area of fatigue, most of this work has been conducted under the load-controlled mode [e.g. see Ref. 1]. Most of these investigations have been conducted using tension-tension ($R > 0$) loading conditions. Only a few studies have been conducted using the strain-controlled mode [e.g. see Ref. 2]. As a result, there is little data available to compare the two loading conditions. Finally, while most of the available work have looked at a variety of MMCs, there has only

been a few investigations that address the relationships between a laminate and its constituent laminae [3,4].

This study concentrates on the response of the 0° and the $0/90$ laminates subjected to fatigue under the load-controlled and strain-controlled mode. The monotonic tensile response is discussed briefly as well. This is then followed by a discussion of the fatigue response (i.e., stress or strain vs. N) under the different control modes. Similarities in the damage mechanisms are then discussed. Finally, a discussion on the fatigue life is presented, where fatigue lives are compared under the different control modes, and a comparison is made between the fatigue lives of 0° and the $0/90$ laminates.

Material and Experimental Setup

The MMC used in this investigation was the Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn (weight percent), titanium alloy reinforced with approximately 36% continuous silicon carbide fibers (SCS-6). This MMC is frequently referred to as SCS-6/Ti-15-3. Three lay-ups were tested: $[0]_8$, $[0]_{32}$, and the $[0/90]_{2s}$. The MMC plates were supplied by Textron Specialty Materials Division, Lowell MA.. They were produced by hot isostatic pressing (hipping) alternate layers of fibers (142 μm diameter) and thin matrix foil.

Two configurations of specimens were used in this study. Both are of the dogbone type, but each had slightly different dimensions. The design of the dogbone used for the 8 ply laminate can be found in [5] while the design used for the 32 ply laminate can be found in [6]. All of the specimens were heat treated at 700°C for 24 hours in a protective environment to stabilize the microstructure of the metastable matrix material [7]. The specimen edges were then polished to remove any damage from cutting. There was no attempt to remove cut fibers from the edges of the specimen.

Specimens were tested in servo-hydraulic load frames described elsewhere [2,6]. All tests were conducted in laboratory air under isothermal conditions at 427°C , but a few were conducted at room temperature for comparison purposes. For the strain-controlled fatigue tests, the strain rate was $1 \times 10^{-3}/\text{s}$ for the 32 ply laminate and $2 \times 10^{-3}/\text{s}$ for the 8 ply laminate. On the other hand, load-controlled testing of the 32 ply laminate was conducted at a frequency equivalent to a strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-3}/\text{s}$. Testing of the 8 ply material was conducted at 1 Hz when the maximum stress was greater than 700 MPa and 10 Hz when it was less than 700 MPa. This resulted in a minimum strain rate of approximately $1.5 \times 10^{-2}/\text{s}$ for these specimens. The post-test specimen preparation involved sectioning the test specimens for microscopic evaluation using optical and scanning electron microscopy. All samples sectioned for microscopic evaluation were taken from the gage section of the tested specimen.

Results and Discussion

Monotonic Response

Fig. 1 shows the monotonic tensile response at 427°C of the $[0]_8$, $[90]_8$, and $[0/90]_{2s}$ laminates. It can be observed that the $[0]_8$ response is nearly linear. Lerch and Saltsman [5] showed that there was no strain rate dependence over the range of 1×10^{-3} to $1 \times 10^{-5}/\text{s}$. A slight non-linear response can be observed above a strain level of 0.55%. This has been shown to be due to plastic deformation of the matrix material [2,8]. On the other hand, the $[90]_8$ response shows a distinctive three stage response where: Stage I is linear elastic, Stage II is dominated by fiber-matrix interface separation, and Stage III is dominated by plastic deformation of the matrix material [8].

The monotonic response of the cross-ply laminate can now be related to that of its basic laminates. Note that this laminate shows the characteristic three stage response of the 90° lamina, although this response is more subtle due to the presence of the 0° plies. All of the failure strains are equivalent within the range of experimental scatter. The strength of the cross-ply is clearly dependent on the strength of the transverse plies. This is illustrated by the fact that its ultimate tensile strength lies between that of the 0° and the 90° laminates.

Fatigue Response

Fig. 2a shows the trends in the maximum and minimum strains for the 0° laminate subjected to fatigue under the fully-reversed ($R_\sigma = -1$), load-controlled mode at a maximum stress of 800 MPa. Fig. 2b shows the response of the 0° laminate under strain-control ($R_\epsilon = 0$). For each loading condition, the response of the thicker laminate and the thinner laminate using an anti-buckling guide is plotted. In the strain-controlled case (Fig. 2b), any difference in the response can be attributed to experimental scatter. On the other hand, a small difference in the response can be observed under the load-controlled mode (Fig. 2a). This is most likely due to the differences in the loading rate, which would result in more matrix creep deformation and hence more strain ratcheting for the slower tests (i.e., the 32 ply material). Thus, for equivalent test conditions, it appears that there is no significant difference in the response of the 32 ply laminate with that of the 8 ply laminate using an anti-buckling guide.

Damage Mechanisms

Fig. 3 shows cross sections of the 0° laminate for the fully-reversed, load and strain controlled conditions. Fig. 3a and 3b are for the 32 ply composite. It can be observed that the dominant damage mechanism is matrix cracking, and it is independent of loading mode or specimen thickness. This is in direct contrast to tension-tension cycling where the fibers are typically over loaded due to load shedding from the matrix as a result of matrix creep [3]. On the other hand, there is no significant load transfer to the fiber due in the case of fully reversed loading. Similar damage was found in the 8 ply laminate. Finally, damage was also found to be independent of fatigue control mode for the cross-ply MMC subjected to fully-reversed loading conditions.

Fatigue Life

Fig. 4a shows the fatigue life of the 8 ply and 32 ply (0°) laminates at 427°C. These lives are plotted versus the maximum stress for both the fully-reversed, load and strain controlled mode. All of the data collapse onto a single curve. The data are also collapsed onto a single curve when plotted as a function of strain range (Fig. 4b). Two significant conclusions can be drawn from these figures. First, there is no dependence on the fatigue control mode, and, second, the use of an anti-buckling guide does not alter the fatigue life. Finally, it appears that an endurance limit exists below a stress level of 400 MPa.

Fig. 5 shows the fatigue life for the $[0/90]_{2s}$ for fully-reversed, load and strain controlled modes at 427°C (HT). Data are also plotted for specimens tested at room temperature (RT) under the fully-reversed, load-controlled mode. As with the unidirectional laminate, the control mode does not affect the fatigue life. Also, the fatigue life is not dependent on the temperature, as has also been shown for the 0° laminate [1].

An attempt was made to collapse the fatigue lives of unidirectional and cross-ply laminates onto a single curve. Gao et al. [4] showed an excellent convergence of the fatigue data based on the maximum stress in the 0° plies. A similar approach is shown in Fig. 6, in which the

fatigue life of the $[0]_8$ and $[0/90]_{2s}$ composites under fully-reversed loading conditions is plotted. It can be observed that the data collapse onto a single curve based on this criterion. This result is independent of the fatigue control mode. Thus, it shows that the affect on the fatigue life of the cross-ply laminate due to damage in the 90° plies can be accounted for solely by the increase in stress in the 0° plies.

Conclusions

- 1) The monotonic tensile response of the cross-ply laminate is closely related to the response of the transverse plies, but the strength is intermediate to the strength of the 0° and 90° orientations.
- 2) The use of a proper anti-buckling guide and thinner test specimens is sufficient for characterizing the fatigue behavior of a MMC.
- 3) The damage mechanisms and fatigue lives are independent of the control mode used during testing.
- 4) The fatigue life based on the stress in the 0° ply of the cross-ply laminate are in agreement with the lives of the unidirectional laminate.

References

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Figure 1 Tensile response of the $[0]_8$, $[90]_8$, and $[0/90]_{2s}$ at 427°C

Figure 2 (a) Maximum and Minimum Strain Responses for the 0° Laminate Under the Load Control Mode ($R_\sigma = -1$) at 427°C (b) Maximum and Minimum Stress Responses for the 0° Laminate Under the Strain Control Mode ($R_\epsilon = 0$) at 427°C

Figure 3 Cross Sections of 32 Ply laminate (a) Load Control ($R_g = -1$)
(b) Strain Control ($R_\epsilon = -1$)

Figure 4 Fatigue life of the 0° Laminate at 427°C on a (a) Maximum Stress Basis (b) Strain Range Basis

Figure 5 Fatigue life of the [0/90]_{2s} Laminate on a Stress Range Basis

Figure 6 Fatigue life of the 0° & [0/90]_{2s} Laminates Based on Maximum Stress in 0° Ply